

Effect of Electrolytes on the Distribution of Acetic Acid between Benzene and Water.

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It is now more or less generally accepted that the Milner-Ghosh-Debye theory of strong electrolytes gives a satisfactory representation of the facts at high dilutions up to a concentration of 0.1N. Above that concentration individual effects appear which cannot be accounted for by the Debye equations. Thus Scatchard and Harned in their attempt to prove the Debye equations have been led to attribute a negative diameter to atoms. Similarly a critical examination of Brönsted's data shows, as has been pointed out by Brönsted himself, that with unsymmetric electrolytes the Debye equations break down even at high dilutions. The Debye equations postulate that the free energy of dilution of electrolytes consists entirely of the work against electrical forces and do not take cognizance of any change in the state of hydration of the ions (*cf.* Nernst).

Further a consideration of the difficulties in the way of the Debye equations has led Bjerrum (*Svensk. Kem. Tidsskr.*, 1926, 38, 2) one of the originators of the hypothesis of complete dissociation to modify the fundamental postulate of this hypothesis by introducing the concept of ion-association which is obviously a formal confession of the failure of the hypothesis of complete dissociation in its original form.

It appears to the writer that before a complete theory of electrolytic dissociation can be established more exhaustive experimental investigations require to be undertaken with a view to elucidate specific differences between the properties of individual ions such as are not accounted for by the Debye equations. We have already indications of such differences even at moderate dilutions and for the simpler inorganic ions.

Subject Matter of Present Investigation.

In the present paper the influence of the common inorganic electrolytes, as for example potassium chloride, sodium chloride,

barium chloride, potassium nitrate, potassium sulphate, lithium chloride, sodium oxalate, lithium sulphate and sodium sulphate on the partition of acetic acid between benzene and water has been studied with a view to examine specific differences between the ions and the limiting concentrations above which such differences appear. The writer would refer to the earlier work on this subject of Dawson (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, 56, 605), of Schreiner (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, 115, 181) and of Cavanagh (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1924, A 106, 243).

The work of McBain and Kam (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1332) on the effect of neutral salts on the partial vapour pressure of acetic acid over its aqueous solutions is most interesting in connection with the present work. They concluded that the increased hydrogen ion concentration on the addition of neutral salts deduced from electromotive force measurements of such solutions are to be referred to increased activity of the ions and not to an increase in dissociation. It is possible to extend the studies of Brønsted on the solubility of salts from a study of the effect of neutral salts on the partial pressure of acetic acid in this system and from a study of similar systems. Measurement of the partition ratio offers an easier experimental procedure than the measurement of vapour pressure. In the present case however it is obvious that the concentration of acetic acid in the benzene phase does not give as reliable a measure of the activity of acetic acid molecules in the solution as is given by its partial pressure in the vapour phase for we are dealing with a solution of acetic acid in aqueous benzene and not in pure benzene. The proportions of water in the benzene phase varies with the activity of water in the aqueous phase which is determined by the concentration and nature of the dissolved electrolyte. On account of the low solubility of water in benzene one may neglect this factor if an interpretation of the results is restricted to a qualitative discussion of the relative effects of different ions under comparable conditions on the activity of acetic acid. Comparison with the stricter procedure of McBain and Kam will give us also the necessary information about the effect of this disturbing factor.* We find that our results are in general agreement with those of McBain and Kam. As we shall see later the present method has also the advantage of being sensitive to slight variations in activity of acetic acid on the addition of salts.

* An independent investigation of the partial pressure of acetic acid over its benzene solution containing varying amounts of water will enable us to quantitatively measure the activity of acetic acid in such solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The distribution of acetic acid between benzene and water was obtained with and without the addition of different concentrations of salts, two concentrations of acid were used one near about 0.5N and the other near about 0.35N, the concentration of the neutral salts was varied from 0.01 to 3 or 4N. Pure chemicals tested before use were always employed. The thermostat was maintained at 35°.

In all cases except otherwise mentioned 50 c.c. of the solution made up by mixing 25 c.c. of the acid of known strength and 25 c.c. of the standard salt solution were introduced together with 50 c.c. of extra pure crystallisable benzene into thoroughly cleansed and dried 100 c.c. Jena glass bottles, the bottles with their contents were thoroughly shaken in a machine for about fifteen minutes, they were then tied on to a rotating axle inside the thermostat to secure equilibrium distribution between the two phases at the required temperature, the equilibrium being attained in less than three hours as found by titration after definite intervals. The bottles were then left in the thermostat with the necks just above the water, measured volumes from the benzene and aqueous phase were taken and titrated against air free standardised baryta solution. Results are given in the following tables.

The five tables under Series I give respectively the results with sodium chloride, potassium chloride, potassium nitrate, barium chloride and potassium sulphate. The first column gives the molar concentration of the salt used, the second gives the 'ionic strength', the third gives the concentration of acid in the benzene phase in terms of normality, the fourth gives the concentration in the aqueous phase, the fifth column gives the ratio (R_1) of the concentrations of the acid in the benzene and in the aqueous phase with the addition of the salt, the sixth gives the same ratio (R_2) obtained without the addition of the salt, the last column gives the percentage increase of the first ratio over the second ratio R_1 , i.e., $100 (R_1 - R_2) / R_2$, this quantity magnifies the relative effect of the added salt and its concentration on the distribution of acetic acid between the two phases (cf. McBain and Kam, *loc cit*).

Electromotive force measurements were also carried out to form an idea of the change in the activity of the hydrogen ion on the addition of neutral salts. The results are given in the six tables under Series II and III, with one portion of the solution the electro

motive force was determined and another portion of the solution was used for determining the distribution ratios by titration. The activity of the hydrogen ion as measured in terms of the hydrogen ion concentration (p_H) using the Nernst equation is given in the last column. The hydrogen ion activity therefore refers to the original solution before partition; the actual values of the electromotive force for the same solutions are given in the appendix. The cell studied was of the type :

Pt(H₂),HAC (salt solution)/sat. KCl/HgCl/Hg (N.KCl), the reference electrode being the normal calomel electrode. The potentiometer used was the "K" type instrument of Leeds and Northrup & Co. The thermostat was maintained at $35^\circ \pm .02^\circ$; extra pure arsenic-free zinc and extra pure acid were used for preparing the hydrogen; under the conditions results reproducible within $\pm .05$ millivolt were obtained in the case of solutions containing higher concentration of the salts; with very dilute solutions of the salts results reproducible to within ± 0.1 millivolt were always obtained. The liquid junction potential has been taken to be zero. Equilibrium in all cases was established in less than four hours.

In Series II and III the first column gives the concentration of the salt; the second gives the "ionic strength"; the third gives the concentration of the acid in terms of normality in the benzene phase; the fourth that in the aqueous phase; the fifth gives the ratio $R_1 = C_B/C_W$, when salt is present; the sixth gives R_2 , the same ratio without addition of salt; the seventh gives the quantity $100(R_1 - R_2)/R_2$; the last gives the p_H value of the original solution before partition. In the fourth and fifth series results are given in the same way with the difference that the electromotive force measurements were made in the solutions after shaking with benzene and determining the distribution ratio by titration; thus the E.M.F. measurements were carried out in solutions in equilibrium with the benzene phase.

SERIES I.

(i) *Conc. of the acid—0.494 N ;
Salt added—Sodium chloride.*

Conc. of salt.	Ionic strength (μ)	C_B	C_W	R_1	R_2	100. $\frac{R_1 - R_2}{R_2}$
.5M	.994	.0128	.481	.0265	.0228	15.9
.25M	.744	.0119	.482	.0247	..	8.34
.1M	.594	.01176	.484	.0243	..	6.2
.05M	.544	.0116	.483	.0241	..	5.46

(ii) *Conc. of the acid—0.497N ;
Salt added—Potassium chloride.*

Conc. of salt.	Ionic strength (μ)	C_B	C_W	R_1	R_2	100. $\frac{R_1 - R_2}{R_2}$
.5M	.997	.0126	.484	.0262	.0228	14.4
.25M	.747	.0120	.485	.0247	..	7.9
.1M	.597	.0113	.486	.0233	..	1.8

(iii) *Conc. of the acid—0.493N ;
Salt added—potassium nitrate.*

5M	.993	.01135	.481	.0238	.02275	4.05
.25M	.743	.011	.483	.0235	..	2.7
.1M	.593	.011	.483	.0235	..	2.7
.05M	.543	.0107	.484	.0231	..	1.17

(iv) *Conc. of the acid—0.497N ;
Salt added—Barium chloride.*

.25M	1.247	.01332	.485	.02745	.0228	20.3
.125M	.872	.0123	.487	.0252	..	10.8
.06M	.647	.0117	.486	.0241	..	5.7
.035M	.572	.01165	.486	.0239	..	5

(v) *Conc. of the acid—0.496N ;
Salt added—Potassium sulphate.*

.25M	1.246	.01245	.482	.0258	.0229	13.1
.125M	.871	.0118	.484	.0246	..	8.06
.05M	.646	.01145	.485	.0236	..	3.6

SERIES II.

(vi) *Conc. of the acid—0.5065N ;
Salt added—Potassium chloride.*

Conc. of salt.	Ionic strength (μ)	C_B	C_W	R_1	R_2	100 $\frac{R_1 - R_2}{R_2}$	p_H
.5M	1.006	.01197	.490	.0244	.0211	15.6	2.356
.25M	.756	.0105	.492	.0214	..	1.2	2.374
.05M	.556	.0105	.495	.0212	..	.8	2.409
No salt0105	.500	2.411

(vii) *Conc. of the acid—0.5065N ;
Salt added—Sodium chloride.*

.5M	1.006	.0121	.4906	.0246	.0211	16.9	2.302
.25M	.756	.01124	.4911	.0229	..	8.5	2.335
.1M	.606	.01117	.4922	.02.7	..	7.6	2.359
.05M	.556	.0111	.4924	.02255	..	6.9	2.374

SERIES III.

(viii) *Conc. of the acid—0.362N;*
Salt added—Barium chloride.

Conc. of salt.	" μ " ionic strength.	C_B	C_w	R_1	R_2	100. $\frac{R_2 - R_1}{R_1}$	P_B
.35M	1.16	.0075	.3596	.0219	.01876	13.4	2.267
.125M	.73	.0071	.355	.0200	"	6.6	2.334
.05M	.51	.0071	.359	.01984	"	5.7	2.367
.025M	.44	.0069	.358	.0194	"	3.4	...
No salt0063	.355	...	"	..	2.415

(ix) *Salt added—Potassium nitrate.*

.5M	.86	.0069	.357	.0195	.01876	3.9	2.402
.1M	.46	.0067	.358	.018765	.01876	.05	2.307

(x) *Salt added—Sodium oxalate.*

.125M369	.353	.0192	.01376	2.3	3.495
.05M	..	.368	.357	.0184	"	—1	3.474
.025M368	.358	.0183	...	—2	3.088

(xi) *Salt added—Potassium sulphate.*

.25M	1.11	.00897	.355	.0196	.0116	4.4	2.809
.125M	.737	.0065	.356	.0184	.01876	—1	2.727
.05M	.512	.0064	.357	.0178	.01876	—5.1	2.651
.025M	.437	2.623

SERIES IV.

(xii) *Conc. of the acid—.35 N;*
Salt added—Potassium chloride.

3 M	3.35	.00908	.341	.0264	.018759	40.7	2.276
2.5M	2.55	.00859	.342	.025	"	34	2.295
2M	2.35	.00823	.3437	.0240	"	28	2.307
1.5M	1.85	.00604	.3429	.0234	"	24.7	2.316
1M	1.35	.00726	.3437	.02112	"	12.5	2.331
.067M	.417	.00.65	.3427	.0194	"	3.4	2.367
No salt0064	.345	...	"	...	2.415

(xiii) Salt added—Sodium chloride.

Conc. of salt.	' μ ' Ionic strength.	C_B	C_w	R_1	R_2	$100 \frac{R_1 - R_2}{R_2}$	p_B
4M	4.35	.0151	.335	.04057	.018759	140.2	1.904
3.5M	3.85	.0137	.336	.04077	"	117.3	1.954
3M	3.35	.0125	.337	.0371	"	97.8	2.013
2.5M	2.85	.0125	.337	.0371	"	97.8	2.021
2M	2.35	.01022	.339	.0301	"	60.6	2.123
1.5M	1.85	.00901	.341	.0264	"	41	2.17
1M	1.35	.00847	.334	.0253	"	34.8	2.238
.2M	.55	.00671	.342	.0196	"	4.4	2.344
.067M	.417	.00659	.344	.0192	"	2.3	2.364
.02M	.37	.00651	.344	.0189	"	.7	2.386

(xiv) Salt added—Barium chloride.

1.25M	4.1	.01029	.3397	.03033	.018759	61.6	1.95
1M	3.35	.00919	.340	.0270	"	44.4	2.019
.75M	2.85	.00865	.341	.0254	"	35.4	2.287
.5M	1.85	.00786	.342	.0231	"	29.1	2.78
.1M	.65	.00677	.338	.0200	"	6.6	2.325
No salt00640	.345	...	"	...	2.415

SERIES V.

(xv) Conc. of acid—5001N;
Salt added—Potassium nitrate.

.5M	2.0	.01077	.485	.0222	.02057	7.9	2.257
1M	1.5	.01065	.4855	.0219	"	6.4	2.289
.2M	.7	.01065	.4856	.0219	"	6.4	2.331
.036M	.536	.01059	.4855	.0218	"	5.9	2.331
.024M	.524	.01059	.4855	.0218	"	5.9	2.336
.012M	.512	.01059	.4855	.0218	...	5.9	...
No salt	..	.01053	.4858

(xvi) Salt added—Sodium sulphate.

255M	1.25	.0118	.485	.0243	.02057	19.1	2.834
.204M	1.11	.0113	.4855	.0234	"	13.7	2.686
.153M	.96	.0119	.48510	.02307	"	12.1	2.597
.102M	.80	.0109	.4855	.0225	"	9.3	2.599
.051M	.68	.01065	.4858	.02192	"	6.5	2.438
.00408M	.512	.01059	.4863	.0217	"	5.4	2.364
.00204M	.50	.01046	.4865	.0215	"	...	2.223

(xvii) Salt added—Lithium chloride.

2.33M	2.89	.0221	.456	.0464	.02057	125.5	1.839
1.863M	2.33	.01936	.477	.0405	"	96.8	1.911
1.397M	1.89	.0167	.481	.0347	"	68.6	1.997
.931M	.69	.0105	.484	.02188	"	6.3	2.173

(xviii) Salt added—Lithium sulphate.

Conc. of salt.	' μ ' Ionic strength.	C_B	C_W	R_1	R_2	$100 \frac{R_1 - R_2}{R_2}$	P_B
.601M	2.90	.01736	.477	.0364	.02057	76.9	2.384
.641M	2.42	.0153	.481	.03177	..	54.4	2.279
.481M	1.94	.0137	.482	.02867	..	39.3	2.228
.320M	1.46	.0121	.483	.02508	..	21.9	...
.160M	.980	.01097	.484	.02267	..	10.2	2.018

Discussion.

As stated in the introduction the results permit only qualitative discussion as to the relative effects of neutral salts at different concentrations on the acetic acid molecules. Colateral measurements could not possibly be undertaken within the time at our disposal. We therefore restrict ourselves to point out the main features of the results.

In the case of all electrolytes excepting potassium sulphate and sodium oxalate the added salt produces increase in activity the magnitude of which increases with increase in concentration. We have three sets of measurements with potassium sulphate Tables No. 5, 11 and 15; the latter two tables deal with a lower concentration of acid than is the case with the first one. It appears that the concentration of the acid used has some effect for at the higher concentration of the acid (*vide* Table 5) the effect is positive at a concentration of .1N and there is a decidedly greater activation. On a close examination of the data it will appear that on account of the low concentration in the benzene layer the relative value of the quantity $100(R_1 - R_2)/R_2$ will be magnified by small experimental errors. At low concentration of the added salts where the change in the activity is small, variations in the above quantity are to be expected from the probable errors of measurements and unless the relative variation is marked it is not possible to draw any definite conclusion. It should be stated here that the above mentioned quantity has no physical significance except that it gives an idea of the extent of activation. Even taking these facts into consideration it is obvious that potassium sulphate behaves in a manner different from the other electrolytes as also from sodium sulphate and lithium sulphate.

McBain and Kam (*loc. cit.*) observed a slight negative effect of sodium sulphate below a concentration of 0.32N of the salt; they however used much lower concentration of the acid between 0.22N and 0.29N. As we have seen the concentration of the acid has also an

influence. Taking our observations in conjunction with those of McBain and Kam it appears that—

(a) The negative activation is the greatest for potassium sulphate and decreases in the order : potassium sulphate > sodium sulphate > lithium sulphate.

(b) That at sufficiently low concentrations of the acid and of these salts this effect can be expected for all the sulphates.

It is likely that further investigation may establish that the negative activation should be ascribed to the sulphate ion and that potassium, sodium and lithium, all produce a positive activation which increases in the order given above, *viz.* lithium > sodium > potassium.

The sulphates also show another characteristic difference, *viz.*, that the activity of the hydrogen ion decreases with increasing concentration of the salt. We are here again dealing with specific influences. We have to take into consideration the formation of HSO_4 ion in explaining this effect. This appears more plausible in view of the fact that sodium oxalate also shows similar effect whereas barium chloride increases the activity of the hydrogen ion at all concentrations though the sulphates and barium chloride are electrolytes of the same type. Potassium nitrate also shows a characteristic behaviour. The activation of the acetic acid molecule is slight and also it has little effect on the activity of the hydrogen ion. With the nitrate also the concentration of the acid seems to have an effect. At lower concentration positive activation is diminished. Also change in activation with the concentration of the salt is small.

Considering the chlorides we again find that the activation is in the order $\text{Li} > \text{Na} > \text{K}$. Barium chloride at the same time ionic strength has a decidedly smaller effect than either lithium or sodium chloride and has more or less the same effect as potassium chloride. The order $\text{Li} > \text{Na} > \text{K}$ is the same as the order of increasing atomic diameters. Dawson (*loc. cit.*) observed for ammonia and iodine the following order of decreasing activating capacity of anions: $\text{SO}_4 > \text{Oxalate} > \text{Cl}' > \text{NO}'_3 > \text{Br}' > \text{I}'$.

The variation in activation of acetic acid molecules with concentration is different for different salts. Here we find, specific differences are not appreciable at very low concentration. To sum up we find that—

(i) The chlorides increase the activity of the hydrogen ion within the range of our investigation as also of acetic acid molecules.

(ii) The ionic strength of the electrolyte is not the only factor but that the sign of the charge of the ion has also to be taken into consideration

(iii) The activating effect of the electrolyte on acetic acid molecule does not always run parallel with its effect on the hydrogen ion

(iv) In the case of the sulphates we are dealing with opposing effects of the cation and the anion on the activation of acetic acid molecules. Such effects are already known. Thus Thomas and Baldwin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1981) have observed that the sulphates behave differently from the chlorides and that at low concentrations the sulphates diminish the activity of the hydrogen ion in solutions of hydrochloric and sulphuric acids but as the concentration increases the activity begins to increase after a certain concentration. There is a characteristic influence of the cation, the magnesium ion showing the greatest increase in activity at the higher concentrations. They also observed that the relative effect of a neutral salt on the activity of hydrogen ion depends on the concentration of the acid (sulphuric)

The question arises whether the effect of the electrolyte on neutral acetic acid molecules is simply made up of its effect on the activities of the hydrogen ion and acetanion or that the activity coefficient of the neutral acetic acid molecules also changes in the presence of neutral electrolytes. The collateral investigations we have referred to are likely to give valuable information on the point. If, as we observe, the sign of the charge and the valency of the ions of neutral electrolytes (apart from their specific influences depending on their diameter or their structure) has an effect it stands to reason that they will have an effect on the anion of the acid; the magnitudes of the two effects will however be different and vary in a different manner with changes in the external conditions. That such an effect is present appears from the fact that though the sulphates decrease the activity of the hydrogen ion (it is specially marked at higher concentrations of the salt) they increase considerably the activity of the acetic acid molecules. It is likely that this in part is due to the activation of the anion but as just stated we are not in a position to say anything definitely so long as we have no knowledge of the effect of electrolytes on the activity of neutral acetic acid molecules.

In conclusion we shall hazard the opinion that the so called agreement with the Debye equations is more or less fortuitous as

the investigations quoted in their support have been too limited in their scope and that factors like existence of undissociated molecules in aqueous solution or the ion association of Bjerram and the hydration of ions are not negligible even at low concentrations of the order of 0.01N.

Since this work was completed a paper by Knight and Hinshelwood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 131, 466) has appeared. The authors from measurements of distribution of HCl between water and benzene conclude that there is definite evidence for the existence of undissociated molecules in the water phase at higher concentration.

In a recent paper Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 174) has given the distribution coefficient of acetic acid between amyl alcohol and aqueous solutions of salts from which he has calculated the extent of hydration. His results however cannot be compared with those of ours so that detailed reference to his paper is unnecessary.

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